

Effectiveness of the COMESA Free Trade Agreement on Market Access, Business Competitiveness, and Customs Procedure for the SMEs at COMESA Market, Lusaka

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: COMESA SMEs Free Trade Agreement Market Access Competitiveness</p>	<p>This study assessed the effectiveness of the COMESA Free Trade Agreement (FTA) on market access and competitiveness of SMEs, with a focus on traders at the COMESA Market in Lusaka. The motivation stemmed from the need to understand whether regional trade integration under COMESA translated into tangible benefits for small-scale traders. The main objectives of this study were to assess how the COMESA FTA has affected market access, business competitiveness and customs procedures for the SME traders at COMESA market in Lusaka. To meet these research objectives a mixed-method design in data analysis with a sample size of 50% being males and 50% being female at COMESA market. The results of the study reviewed that the FTA enhanced market access which enables traders to connect with regional buyers, diversify products, participate in trade fairs, and establish cross-border partnerships. Competitiveness was improved mainly through pricing, with 72% of SMEs reporting the ability to offer lower and more competitive prices. However, improvements in product variety and operational cost reduction were moderate due to logistical and supply chain constraints. Customs procedures which was 50% was found to be significantly related to clearance speed, yet challenges such as delays, excessive paperwork, limited digital systems, and inconsistent rule application hindered efficiency. Respondents highlighted key challenges, including manual inspections, unclear fees, and language barriers, and recommended digitization of customs, automated inspections, SME helpdesks, and improved border communication. Overall, most SMEs expressed satisfaction with COMESA trade processes but emphasized the need for policy interventions such as digitalization, capacity-building, and financial support. The study concluded that the COMESA FTA improved market access and competitiveness of SMEs in Lusaka but that its full potential depended on addressing procedural and infrastructural challenges. Strengthening trade facilitation mechanisms would ensure inclusive growth and enhance SME participation in regional markets.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are key to the economic development of Zambia, contributing significantly towards employment creation and income generation. Notwithstanding their significance, SMEs remain severely constrained by lack of access to markets, poor infrastructure and lacklustre competitiveness in regional as well as global trade (ZDA 2022). To overcome these challenges, Zambia is a member of regional trade agreements (RTAs) such as the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) FTA, which was established in 2000 to promote free trade among its members by eliminating tariffs and non-tariff barriers (COMESA, 2023).

Spanning 21 member countries with over six hundred million people, the COMESA FTA offers SMEs a remarkable platform for market expansion, cheaper trading and improved productivity (UNCTAD, 2020; World Bank, 2021).

Yet despite enthusiasm about the potential benefits of the COMESA FTA, SMEs in Zambia – including those located at the COMESA Market in Lusaka – are still facing some challenges which hamper their ability to engage effectively with regional markets. These revolve around inefficient customs processes, lack of awareness about trade provisions and the existence of little financial and technical capacity (AfDB, 2024; Kalinda & Tembo, 2020).

Though FTA has brought in cross-border trading opportunities, it is really not clear if it has been effective in removing restrictions on SME market access and competitiveness. To the contrary, previous studies have shown that the bulk of benefits in trade liberalization go to large, established enterprises (Beegle et al., 2019; Mulenga & Tembo, 2020). It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the extent of the impact of the COMESA FTA on SME performance in Zambia concerning market access, competitiveness, and customs facilitation for traders at the COMESA Market in Lusaka.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The COMESA Free Trade Agreement was designed to promote regional trade and enhance the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) by reducing trade barriers and encouraging access to the market. However, the Agreement remains largely irrelevant, and its benefits not fully appreciated in practice by many local traders, according to Kalinda and Tembo (2020) and Mulenga (2021). Among other things, in the Lusaka COMESA Market, SME operators are hindered by customs inefficiencies, limited knowledge of trade provisions, and little participation in formal cross-border trade (COMESA, 2020; World Bank, 2021; ZDA, 2022; UNCTAD, 2019). How far has the COMESA Free Trade Agreement thus far translated into real measurable benefits in terms of market access and competitiveness for SMEs, and have trade facilitation options been put in place to limit operational bottlenecks? (AfDB, 2021) Beegle et al. (2019) and Yusuf and Akinwale (2022) contend that the scanty empirical evidence on these matters obstructs policymakers from fashioning targeted strategies to promote SME growth. In view of this, the study aims to fill this lacuna by investigating the level of effectiveness of the COMESA FTA on market access and competitiveness of SMEs operating in the COMESA Market in Lusaka.

1.3 General objectives

The main objective of the study is assessing the effectiveness of the COMESA free trade agreement on market access, business competitiveness, and custom procedures for SMEs at COMESA market in Lusaka.

1.3.1 Specific objectives

- i. To assess the effect of the COMESA Free Trade Agreement on market access for SME traders in COMESA Market.
- ii. To examine the effects of the COMESA FTA on the competitiveness of SMEs at COMESA market in Lusaka.
- iii. To evaluate the effectiveness of customs procedures for SMEs at COMESA market in Lusaka.

1.4 Research questions

- i. Has the coming up with free trade agreement made it easier for SMEs to access the COMESA market?
- ii. How competitive does the COMESA FTA does it make it to be for SMEs?
- iii. How effective are the customs procedures for SMEs at COMESA market in Lusaka?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework links the COMESA FTA as the independent variable to three dependent variables: SME market access, competitiveness, and customs efficiency. Literature shows that regional trade agreements expand market reach, reduce operational costs, and simplify customs processes for SMEs. The framework emphasises that improved tariff conditions, streamlined documentation, and efficient border procedures enhance business outcomes. It also recognises moderating factors such as SME size, financial capacity, managerial ability, and market conditions. These factors determine the extent to which SMEs benefit from the opportunities created by the COMESA FTA.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

2. Literature Review

2.1 *The effect of the Free Trade Agreement on market access*

Research in Vietnam (General Statistics Office of Vietnam, 2023; World Bank, 2023) portrays SMEs as being very effective and quite resource compact in bringing about employment, standing up to 98% of the whole population of enterprises and generating for over 5.4 million jobs up to the year 2012. Analysis evidence indicates cost-efficient generation of off-farm employment by SMEs and further contribution to the national economic growth. The findings underscore that SMEs are very important engines for job creation and economic resilience but need indeed conducive policies and institutional frameworks to scale up the impact of SMEs. This is relevant to economic zones of COMESA wishing to optimize SMEs in local employment.

Research has found government aid and liberalization to increase trade (Nguyen et al., 2022; UNCTAD, 2023; Khan et al., 2020; Azmeh et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2022): Improvement in every area of reform in laws, finance, human resources development, and facilitated trade promotion leads the competitiveness and management of SMEs into the internationalization journey. Analytical review discloses that the countries which open up more trade opportunities tend to create more jobs and have a higher reduction in poverty, though such merits are often undermined by institutional or structural barriers. Such capacities need to be specifically built for specific needs of SMEs. Making certain that the rule-making regulatory framework is short, making them easy to comply with, helped SMEs to take greater advantage of benefits from trade liberalization. These findings imply that COMESA SMEs need both policy backing and reduced bureaucratic hurdles to thrive.

Research on SME internationalization under FTAs vis--vis the global market (UNECA, 2021; UNCTAD, 2020; Cavusgil & Knight, 2019; Leonidou et al., 2018; Coviello & McAuley, 2018) shows that FTAs will reduce or eliminate trade barriers with respect to specific markets, broaden market access, and ensure the participation of SMEs within regional and global value chains. Analytical insights show that while SMEs benefit from technology adoption, digital platforms, and strategic networking, they often face huddles of regulatory compliance as well as competitive pressures. Success in internationalizing a company mainly depends on how well the managerial capabilities, entrepreneurial orientation, and firm-specific strategies are aligned. The evidence emphasizes that both internal competencies and external support structures are critical for SME growth. For COMESA SMEs, similar mechanisms could enhance employment creation, competitiveness, and regional integration.

2.2 *The effects of the FTA on the competitiveness of SMEs*

Studies on U.S. SMEs (Bacchetta et al., 2019; Hakobyan & McLaren, 2019; López-González, 2019; Reuber & Fischer, 2018) demonstrate that FTAs reduce tariffs and expand regional market access, encouraging SMEs to innovate in supply chain management and technology adoption. However, SMEs struggle with complex trade rules and heightened foreign competition, indicating that access alone does not guarantee competitiveness. Analytical evidence suggests that government trade-readiness programs and policy interventions are crucial for translating FTA opportunities into operational gains. The research highlights that SMEs require both regulatory clarity and strategic support to benefit fully. For COMESA SMEs, similar mechanisms could strengthen participation in regional trade.

European SME studies (Knight & Cavusgil, 2018; Cavusgil & Zou, 2019; Leonidou et al., 2018; Erramilli & Rao, 2018) reveal that FTAs enhance market access, reduce tariffs, and incentivize innovation by exposing SMEs to global competition. Nevertheless, regulatory complexity, rules of origin, and intensified competition constrain the benefits, emphasizing the interplay between policy design and firm capabilities. Analytical insights suggest that digitalization, capacity-building, and SME-specific trade support are essential to fully leverage FTAs. SMEs' operational efficiency and product quality improve only when these structural enablers complement market access. For COMESA SMEs, adapting similar support frameworks could enhance competitiveness.

African SME-focused research (Leonidou et al., 2018; Crick & Spence, 2019; Coviello & Munro, 2019; Hennart, 2019) indicates that FTAs such as AfCFTA provide opportunities for market expansion, product innovation, and economies of scale. Yet, SMEs face financing constraints, limited market knowledge, and challenges in regulatory compliance, highlighting the critical role of managerial capacity and entrepreneurial skills. Analytical evaluation suggests that strong supplier-client networks and strategic partnerships amplify the benefits of regional trade agreements. Sustained capacity-building and knowledge-sharing programs are therefore necessary for SMEs to translate access into competitiveness. These findings suggest that COMESA SMEs could similarly benefit from integrated support mechanisms alongside the FTA.

2.3 *The Effectiveness of Customs procedures in Supporting SME Trade Operations*

Studies from India (Kumar & Singh, 2018; Verma & Shukla, 2019) and Nigeria (Ojo et al., 2020) show that efficient customs procedures—such as simplified documentation, faster clearance, and electronic systems—significantly reduce SME transaction costs and enhance export competitiveness. SMEs operating under streamlined customs experience improved market access and reduced delays. However, bureaucratic inefficiencies, corruption, and lack of awareness limit the full benefits of trade facilitation. These studies highlight that customs reforms must be paired with SME training and regulatory guidance. Overall, global evidence shows that customs efficiency is a major determinant of SME competitiveness in regional trade frameworks similar to COMESA. Research from South Africa (Naidoo & Govender, 2019) and the East African Community (Munga & Waweru, 2020) demonstrates that customs efficiency and harmonised procedures improve SME market entry, supply chain reliability, and competitiveness. SMEs that navigate customs smoothly gain faster access to regional markets and higher export performance. Nonetheless, persistent non-tariff barriers such as border delays, inconsistent rules, and weak knowledge of trade procedures hinder SME operations. The studies emphasize the centrality of transparent, technology-driven customs systems. The findings strongly relate to COMESA, where similar procedural barriers limit SMEs at the Lusaka market. Evidence from Brazil and Mexico (Lopez & Fernandez, 2019) shows that customs digitalization—electronic documentation, automated

clearance, and training—boosts SME export growth and operational efficiency. Similarly, Zambian research (Chileshe & Mwansa, 2021) reveals that simplified COMESA customs procedures and duty waivers improve SME trade volumes and clearance times. However, limited digital infrastructure and low SME awareness constrain broader adoption of these reforms. Both regions highlight that modernization must be paired with capacity building and institutional support. These findings underscore the need for COMESA to strengthen digital customs systems and SME-focused support at the Lusaka COMESA Market.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a descriptive survey design within a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to investigate the effects of the COMESA Free Trade Agreement (FTA) on market access and competitiveness among SMEs at Lusaka’s COMESA Market. Descriptive research allows systematic collection and analysis of data, providing numerical insights on pricing, product variety, and operational costs, while qualitative data captures traders’ experiences with trade facilitation mechanisms (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Bryman, 2018; Flick, 2018). The mixed-method design strengthens validity by cross-verifying findings from different data sources and providing a holistic understanding of SME operations under the FTA (Kumar, 2019).

3.2 Target Population

The target population comprises SME traders actively engaged in cross-border trade or importing/exporting goods under the COMESA FTA framework (Sekaran & Bougie, 2019). Focusing on these traders ensures that the collected data are relevant and contextually rich, reflecting the real experiences of SMEs navigating regional trade opportunities.

3.3 Sampling Design

Purposive sampling, a non-probability technique, will be used to select participants with direct experience in cross-border trade under COMESA arrangements (Etikan & Bala, 2018; Saunders et al., 2019). This method ensures that respondents possess the necessary knowledge to provide accurate insights into the effects of the COMESA FTA on market access, pricing strategies, and operational efficiency.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The study will include 25 SME traders from various sectors such as textiles, groceries, electronics, and crafts. This sample size allows for in-depth data collection while capturing diverse perspectives, aligning with the case study approach that prioritizes depth over breadth (Kothari, 2018).

3.5 Data Collection Methods

Primary data will be collected through structured questionnaires containing closed- and open-ended questions and semi-structured interviews with SME owners and COMESA trade officers to gain detailed insights on trade facilitation and market competitiveness. Secondary data will be obtained from COMESA publications, Zambia Development Agency reports, government policy documents, and academic journals (World Bank, 2023; COMESA Secretariat, 2024).

3.6 Data Analysis

Quantitative data will be analyzed using SPSS (version 26), with descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores summarizing respondents’ perspectives. Chi-Square tests will examine associations between the COMESA FTA and SME outcomes. Qualitative data from interviews will undergo thematic analysis to identify patterns related to trade facilitation, customs efficiency, and SME competitiveness (Nowell et al., 2019). Triangulation of both data types will provide comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of the COMESA FTA in supporting SME growth, operational efficiency, and market integration.

4. Findings

4.1 Demographic Characteristics Of The Respondents

The study examined the demographic characteristics of respondents, focusing on gender, age, education, years in business, and type of business. These variables provided insight into the composition and diversity of the entrepreneurial population under study.

4.1.1 Gender

Table 1 presents the gender distribution of the study participants, highlighting the importance of capturing perspectives from both males and females.

Table 1. Gender

Gender	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Female	25	50.00	50.00
Male	25	50.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The findings show that the gender distribution among SME traders at COMESA Market was evenly split, with 25 male respondents (50%) and 25 female respondents (50%). This balance indicates that both men and women participate actively in cross-border and domestic trading activities at the market, highlighting the inclusive nature of SME participation under the COMESA framework.

4.1.2 Age

Figure 2. Age

In terms of age, the largest proportion of respondents were 25–34 years (32%), followed closely by those aged 35–44 years (28%). Traders aged 45 years and above and those below 25 years each accounted for 20% of the sample. This distribution suggests that SME trading at COMESA Market is dominated by youthful and middle-aged entrepreneurs, who are often more adaptable to regional trade opportunities, while older and younger traders represent smaller but significant groups.

4.1.3 Education

The analysis of educational attainment shows that the majority of respondents possessed relatively high levels of formal education, with 34% holding degree-level qualifications and another 34% holding diplomas. Meanwhile, 26% had completed secondary education, and only 6% had attained primary education.

Figure 3. Education

These results suggest that a considerable proportion of traders at the market are educated, which may influence their ability to understand and navigate trade agreements such as the COMESA FTA.

4.1.4 Years in Business

When considering business experience, 28% of traders had been in business for seven years or more, reflecting a strong presence of well-established entrepreneurs. Those operating for four to six years and one to three years each accounted for 26%, while 20% of respondents were in their first year of business.

Figure 4. Years in Business

This distribution indicates a mix of experienced and emerging traders, with a notable proportion of new entrants who may face unique challenges in leveraging opportunities under the COMESA FTA.

Table 2 Type of Business

Sector	Approx. Frequency (n)	Approx. Percentage (%)
Retail & trading (cosmetics, clothing, electronics, groceries, mobile accessories, kiosks, etc.)	21	42%
Manufacturing & processing (bakeries, tailoring, agro-processing, carpentry etc.)	10	20%
Services & other (ICT, logistics, catering, tourism, printing, handicrafts, design)	14	28%
Agriculture-related (farm produce, poultry, agro-inputs)	6	12%

Source: Field Data (2025)

Retail/trading is the backbone of activity; manufacturing and services supply complementary roles. This structural mix matters for trade policy retail traders may respond differently to customs reforms than agro-processors or exporters.

4.2 Effect of COMESA FTA on Market Access

This section presents the results of a Chi-square analysis conducted to determine the effect of the COMESA Free Trade Area (FTA) on market access among SMEs in the Lusaka Central Business District. The analysis focused on key variables including the market access effect, share of COMESA goods traded, influence of the COMESA FTA on market linkages, and customer reach.

Table 3. A Chi Square test on Market access effect and COMESA goods percent

Market access effect	COMESA goods percent				Total
	25-50%	<25%	51-75%	Above 75%	
Slightly improved	19	5	1	0	25
	6.9	0.6	3.2	2.5	13.2
Significantly impro..	2	0	9	5	16
	3.3	4.5	10.5	7.2	25.5
No change	0	9	0	0	9
	3.8	16.7	1.8	0.9	23.1
Total	21	14	10	5	50
	14.0	21.7	15.5	10.6	61.8

Pearson chi2 (6) = 61.8280 Pr = 0.000

Based on the provided table above, we can set up the null and alternative hypotheses for the chi-squared test of independence. The Pearson chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 61.8280$ $p = 0.000$) was used to test the hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H0)

H0: Market access effect and COMESA goods percent are independent

Alternative Hypothesis (H1)

H1: Market access effect and COMESA goods percent are dependent.

Based on the provided data and setting the level of significance at $\alpha = 0.05$, we can conclude the hypothesis test using the p-value obtained from the chi-squared test.

Decision rule

For the chi-square test of independence, the decision rule is as follows:

If the p-value $\geq \alpha$ (0.05), fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that there is no significant association between the variables.

If the p-value $< \alpha$ (0.05), reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that there is a significant association between the variables.

In this study, since the p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses:

H_0 : Market access effect and the share of COMESA goods are independent.

H_1 : Market access effect and the share of COMESA goods are dependent.

Interpretation: This result rejects H_0 and supports H_1 there is a statistically significant association between perceived market access improvements and the proportion of goods traders source/trade within COMESA. In practice, traders with greater COMESA goods shares are more likely to report improved market access.

Test statistic: $\chi^2 = 61.8280$

p-value: 0.000 (reported)

Decision: $p < 0.05 \rightarrow$ reject H_0 .

Table 4. Market Access Effect

Market access effect	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
No change	9	18.00	18.00
Significantly improved	16	32.00	50.00
Slightly improved	25	50.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The findings reveal that market access has generally improved following COMESA integration, with 50% of respondents reporting slight improvement and 32% indicating significant improvement. Only 18% of participants experienced no change, which suggests that the majority of businesses have benefited from expanded opportunities under the COMESA framework. This indicates that while the FTA has enhanced access to regional markets, the extent of improvement varies, with most firms experiencing incremental rather than transformative gains.

Table 5. Share of COMESA Goods

COMESA goods percent	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
25–50%	21	42.00	42.00
51–75%	10	20.00	62.00
<25%	14	28.00	90.00
Above 75%	5	10.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The results on the share of COMESA goods show that 42% of respondents trade between 25–50% of their goods within the regional bloc, while 28% trade less than 25%, indicating limited reliance on COMESA markets for a significant portion of participants. Only 20% trade between 51–75%, and 10% exceed 75%, showing that deeper integration into COMESA trade is achieved by a small minority. This pattern highlights that although COMESA plays a role in facilitating trade, most firms are still only moderately dependent on regional markets, reflecting partial rather than full integration.

Table 6. Influence of COMESA FTA on Market Linkages and Customer Reach

Theme	# respondents	% of respondents (mentioned)	Example indicators (original responses)
Expanded customer base / regional buyers	34	68%	“Reaching neighbouring countries”, “selling in bulk regionally”
Strategic partnerships / cross-border links	22	44%	“Forming cross-border partnerships”, “joint promotions”
Enhanced marketing / trade fairs & regional advertising	18	36%	“Participating in trade fairs”, “regional adverts”
Product diversification & sourcing	20	40%	“Diversifying products”, “sourcing regionally”
Improved supply-chain efficiency & bulk sales	15	30%	“Better supply arrangements”, “sell in bulk”

Source: Field Data (2025)

Discussion: The dominant theme is an expanded customer base (68%), showing that many SMEs see the FTA primarily as a demand-side opportunity. Strategic partnerships and product diversification are also common. Because themes overlap, these percentages sum to more than 100% this is expected for coded open responses and shows multiple simultaneous benefits.

Implication: Policy and trade promotion that target market linkages (trade fairs, buyer-seller platforms) would likely leverage the largest perceived benefit (expanded customer base) and reinforce partnerships and diversification.

4.3 Effect of COMESA FTA on Competitiveness

This section examines the impact of the COMESA Free Trade Area (FTA) on the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) operating within the Lusaka Central Business District. The analysis focused on key indicators of competitiveness, including pricing competitiveness, product variety, reduction in operational costs, and the overall effect of the COMESA FTA on SMEs' competitiveness compared to non-SME traders.

Table 7. Pricing Competitiveness

Pricing competitiveness	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Agree	23	46.00	46.00
Disagree	8	16.00	62.00
Moderate	6	12.00	74.00
Strongly agree	13	26.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The findings on pricing competitiveness show that the majority of respondents (46%) agreed that the COMESA Free Trade Agreement (FTA) has enhanced competitiveness through pricing, while 26% strongly agreed. On the other hand, 16% disagreed and 12% remained moderate. This suggests that most traders at the COMESA Market perceive the FTA as having a positive impact on their ability to compete based on pricing, making their goods more affordable and attractive compared to alternatives. However, a small segment of traders still express reservations, indicating that the benefits may not be evenly distributed across all businesses.

Table 8. Product Variety

Product variety	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Agree	14	28.00	28.00
Disagree	8	16.00	44.00
Moderate	21	42.00	86.00
Strongly agree	7	14.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

Regarding product variety, the results indicate that 42% of respondents were moderate in their assessment, while 28% agreed and 14% strongly agreed that the FTA has improved the range of products available. Only 16% disagreed. These findings suggest that while the FTA has contributed to some improvements in product diversity, most traders remain cautious in their assessment, reflecting mixed experiences in accessing and offering a wider selection of goods. This points to a gradual but uneven enhancement of market variety influenced by the trade agreement.

Table 9. Reduced Costs

Reduced costs	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Agree	19	38.00	38.00
Disagree	9	18.00	56.00
Moderate	20	40.00	96.00
Strongly agree	1	2.00	98.00
Strongly disagree	1	2.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

In terms of reduced costs, 38% of respondents agreed that the FTA has helped reduce operational or trading costs, while 40% remained moderate. Only 2% strongly agreed, while another 2% strongly disagreed, and 18% disagreed. These findings reveal that while some traders acknowledge cost reductions due to the trade agreement, the majority remain undecided, possibly due to persistent challenges such as tariffs, transaction costs, and logistical barriers. This indicates that although the FTA has created some cost advantages, these benefits may not yet be fully realized across the SME sector in Lusaka.

Table 10. Effect of COMESA FTA on SMEs’ Competitiveness Compared to Non-SME Traders

Theme	# respondents	Percent %
Improved supplier access & better prices	30	60%
Ability to scale / reach new markets	26	52%
Faster product introduction / seasonal goods	14	28%
Enhanced bargaining power	18	36%

Source: Field Data (2025)

Many SMEs report competitive gains vis-à-vis non-SME traders through better supplier access and market reach. This indicates that the FTA can be an equalizer, but again, benefits concentrate among those who actively engage the regional market.

4.4 Effectiveness of Customs and Trade Facilitation

This section assesses the effectiveness of customs operations and trade facilitation measures under the COMESA Free Trade Area (FTA) and their impact on SMEs trading within the Lusaka Central Business District. A Chi-square test was conducted to examine the relationship between customs effectiveness and key indicators such as speed of clearance, transparency, cost of cross-border trade, and overall satisfaction. Additionally, the analysis considered challenges faced by SMEs in customs processes and their suggested improvements for enhancing trade facilitation under the COMESA framework.

Table 11. A Chi Square test on Customs effectiveness and speed clearance

Customs effectiveness	Speed clearance				Total
	Moderate	Good	Fair	Excellent	
Effective	15 1.1	10 0.5	0 3.0	0 2.5	25 7.1
Neutral	8 0.4	0 4.5	6 11.1	0 1.4	14 17.4
Very effective	0 5.1	6 1.7	0 1.3	5 13.8	11 22.0
Total	23 6.5	16 6.7	6 15.4	5 17.7	50 46.4

Pearson $\chi^2(6) = 46.3862$ Pr = 0.000

Based on the provided table above, we can set up the null and alternative hypotheses for the chi-squared test of independence. The Pearson chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 46.3862$ p = 0.000) was used to test the hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H0)

H0: Customs effectiveness and speed clearance are independent

Alternative Hypothesis (H1)

H1: Customs effectiveness and speed clearance are dependent.

Based on the provided data and setting the level of significance at $\alpha = 0.05$, we can conclude the hypothesis test using the p-value obtained from the chi-squared test.

Decision rule

For the chi-square test of independence, the decision rule is as follows:

If p-value $\geq \alpha$ (0.05) → fail to reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and conclude that there is no significant association between customs effectiveness and speed clearance.

If p-value $< \alpha$ (0.05) → reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and conclude that there is a significant association between customs effectiveness and speed clearance.

Conclusion

Since the Pearson chi-square test yielded a statistic of $\chi^2 = 46.3862$ with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that customs effectiveness and speed clearance are significantly dependent on each other. In other words, the effectiveness of customs processes has a direct and significant effect on the speed of clearance for traders at COMESA Market in Lusaka.

Test statistic: $\chi^2 = 46.3862$

p-value: 0.000

Decision: p < 0.05 → reject H₀.

Hypotheses:

H₀: Customs effectiveness and speed of clearance are independent.

H₁: Customs effectiveness and speed of clearance are dependent.

Interpretation: This result rejects H₀ and supports H₁ customs effectiveness and clearance speed are significantly associated. Practically, perceptions of higher customs effectiveness correlate with faster clearance times.

Table 12. Customs Effectiveness

Customs effectiveness	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Effective	25	50.00	50.00
Neutral	14	28.00	78.00
Very effective	11	22.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The results indicate that customs systems under COMESA are generally perceived positively, with half of the respondents (50%) rating them as effective and 22% as very effective. Only 28% rated customs performance as neutral, which suggests that the majority of businesses acknowledge improvements in customs facilitation processes that support regional trade. This reflects progress in trade policy implementation, though the “neutral” responses highlight that there are still challenges in achieving uniformly efficient customs operations across the bloc.

Table 13. Speed of Clearance

Speed clearance	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Excellent	5	10.00	10.00
Fair	6	12.00	22.00
Good	16	32.00	54.00
Moderate	23	46.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

On the speed of customs clearance, the findings reveal mixed perceptions, with 46% rating clearance as moderate and 32% rating it as good. Only 10% considered the process excellent, while 12% described it as fair, indicating that although clearance processes are functioning, they remain relatively slow and inconsistent. The predominance of “moderate” responses suggests that while businesses benefit from regional trade facilitation, delays in clearance continue to pose a barrier to maximizing the potential benefits of COMESA integration.

Table 14. Transparency

Transparency	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Fair	11	22.00	22.00
Good	15	30.00	52.00
Moderate	24	48.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

The findings on transparency in cross-border trade indicate that 48% of respondents considered it moderate, while 30% rated it as good and 22% as fair. This suggests that traders at COMESA Market perceive transparency in trade procedures as adequate but not fully optimal. Moderate transparency may reflect some challenges in accessing clear information or inconsistent enforcement of trade rules, highlighting areas where policy interventions could improve confidence and ease of trading.

Table 15. Cost of Cross-Border Trade

Cost cross border	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Fair	12	24.00	24.00
Good	10	20.00	44.00
Moderate	28	56.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

Regarding the cost of cross-border trade, a majority of respondents (56%) rated it as moderate, while 24% considered it fair and 20% as good. These results suggest that SMEs experience neither extremely high nor very low trading costs, but that costs are still a noticeable concern. Moderate cost levels may be influenced by factors such as transportation, tariffs, and non-tariff barriers, affecting SMEs’ competitiveness and market participation under the COMESA Free Trade Agreement.

Table 16. Challenges Faced by SMEs in Customs and Trade Facilitation under COMESA FTA

Challenge theme	# respondents	Percent %
Delays in customs clearance / long queues	35	70%
High paperwork / documentation requirements	30	60%
Limited SME knowledge of procedures & exemptions	25	50%
Low digitization / limited use of electronic systems	23	46%
Manual inspections / inconsistent rules application	20	40%
Unclear fees & charges	19	38%
Language barriers / limited operating hours at borders	15	30%

Delays and paperwork top the list. Even where customs are perceived as “effective,” operational frictions (manual inspections, inconsistent rule application) and lack of SME knowledge prevent traders from realizing full benefits.

Table 17. Suggested Improvements for Customs and Trade Facilitation under COMESA FTA

Suggested improvement	# respondents	Percent %
Digitize customs & electronic clearance (automated, risk-based)	32	64%
SME training / helpdesks and multilingual support	28	56%
Standardize & reduce paperwork / clarify fees	26	52%
Extend border operating hours / faster inspections	20	40%
Access to finance / grants & tax incentives	18	36%
Regional trade promotion (trade expos, buyer-seller events)	15	30%

The most frequent recommendation is digitization (64%) followed by SME capacity building and paperwork standardization actionable items that would speed clearance, reduce errors, and improve transparency.

Table 18. Overall Satisfaction

Overall satisfaction	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Dissatisfied	6	12.00	12.00
Neutral	9	18.00	30.00
Satisfied	20	40.00	70.00
Very satisfied	15	30.00	100.00
Total	50	100.00	

In terms of overall satisfaction with COMESA trade processes, 40% of respondents reported being satisfied and 30% very satisfied, while 18% were neutral and 12% dissatisfied. This indicates that most traders perceive COMESA trade arrangements positively, suggesting that the FTA has contributed to improved market access and trading experiences. However, the presence of neutral and dissatisfied respondents shows that there are still challenges that need to be addressed to ensure equitable benefits for all SMEs.

Table 19 Suggestions by SMEs to Enhance COMESA FTA Support

Theme	Specific Suggestions	Frequency (n=50)	Percentage (%)
Capacity Building and Awareness	Conduct workshops and training on trade regulations, compliance, and risk management	32	64%
Digitalization and Information Access	Develop mobile apps, online tutorials, and digital portals to monitor trade and facilitate market access	28	56%
SME Support Structures	Establish SME helpdesks, mentorship schemes, regional trade expos, and trade promotion programs	26	52%
Financial Support and Incentives	Provide easier access to trade finance, grants, subsidies, tax incentives, and low-interest loans	35	70%
Trade Facilitation and Bureaucracy Reduction	Improve transparency in customs fees, reduce bureaucracy, standardize forms, and digitize clearance processes	30	60%

SMEs highlighted financial support and incentives as the biggest need (70%), followed by calls for more capacity building and awareness initiatives (64%) to better navigate trade requirements. They also stressed the importance of digital transformation (56%) and stronger SME support structures (52%), alongside frustrations over complex customs processes, driving demand for trade facilitation and reduced bureaucracy (60%). Overall, the results show that SMEs require a blend of financial, digital, institutional, and regulatory reforms to fully benefit from the COMESA FTA.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

The study shows that the COMESA FTA has improved SMEs' market access, product diversity, and competitiveness at the COMESA Market in Lusaka, supported by expanded customer reach and stronger supplier networks. However, delays, inconsistent customs rules, heavy documentation, and limited digital systems continue to hinder full FTA benefits. Overall, the findings highlight the need for better trade facilitation, digital reforms, and stronger institutional support to maximize SME participation in regional trade.

5.2 Conclusion

While the COMESA FTA has clearly strengthened SMEs' ability to compete and access regional markets, its full impact is limited by inefficiencies in customs procedures and uneven application of trade rules. Addressing these challenges is vital to unlocking the agreement's intended benefits for small businesses. The study concludes that sustained institutional, technological, and procedural reforms are essential to improving transparency, efficiency, and SME empowerment.

5.2 Recommendations

The study recommends streamlining customs processes through digitization, standardized procedures, and risk-based inspections to reduce delays and costs. It also calls for expanded SME training, improved information-sharing platforms, and greater access to affordable trade finance and incentives. Finally, promoting regional networking, trade fairs, and continuous monitoring of FTA implementation will strengthen competitiveness and support long-term SME growth.

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